

Pollen Characterization of Some Tropical Flora of Kollapur Revenue Division of Nagarkurnool District of Telangana State, South India

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Abstract

The present paper deals with the ongoing pollen morphological studies of the flora of Kollapur division of Nagarkurnool district of Telangana state, India. Pollen morphology of fifteen taxa referable to thirteen families was analysed. Pollen morphology of *Alstonia scholaris*, *Cordia sebestena*, *Dichrostachis cinerea*, *Dodonea viscosa*, *Gyrocarpus americanus*, *Leucophyllum frutescens*, *Mimosa aculeticarpa*, *Mimosa pudica*, *Nyctanthes arbor tristis*, *Prunus mahleb*, *Santalum album*, *Senna occidentalis*, *Styrax officinalis*, *Syzygium cumini*, *Zizyphus mauritiana*, were analysed under light microscopy. The pollen slides were prepared by using standard acetolysis method (Erdtman, 1960). In this study, pollen morphological features including grain units, size and shape, number and character of apertures, exine sculpture were examined. Pollen grain units were mostly monads but tetrads and octads were also recorded. The shapes of all pollen grain varied from oblate, oblate-spheroidal, prolate, prolate-spheroidal to spheroidal. Apertures were simple and composite types, colpate, colpporate and porate aperture types were characterized in the pollen taxa. The exine sculpturing patterns of studied pollen taxa ranged from psilate, verrucate, microreticulate, reticulate, retipilate, striate-rugulate, and scabrate.

Keywords: Tropical flora, Pollen morphology, Kollapur division, Nagarkurnool district, Telangana state, India.

Introduction

Kollapur region is an area spanning the Nallamala forest on the banks of the river Krishna of Nagarkurnool district in the state of Telangana. Kollapur is located at a distance of 178 kms from Hyderabad and 50.3 Kms from Nagarkurnool. Most of the Nallamala region along the Krishna River was under Kollapur division and is located at 18.0°N 79.58°E. It has an average elevation of 458 metres (1503 feet) and is settled in the central Deccan plateau and northern part of Nallamalla Hills with dry deciduous forests towards the southern region of the Nagarkurnool district. The Tiger Reserve is rich in flora and fauna and the floral diversity is moderately rich with medicinal properties. Pollen morphology is one of the most

significant tool for the taxonomic study as well as systematics of plant taxa. The present paper is a part of an ongoing work on pollen morphological studies of the flora of Kollapur revenue division and it deals with the study of pollen characters of fifteen taxa recorded from the study area.

Materials and Methods

Polleniferous material of fifteen genera of thirteen families during their flowering period were collected for palynological studies from Kollapur division of Nagarkurnool district of Telangana state south India (Map-1 and II). The flowering plants collected include *Alstonia scholaris*, *Cordia sebestena*, *Dichrostachis cinerea*, *Dodonea*

viscosa, *Gyrocarpus americanus*, *Leucophyllum frutescens*, *Mimosa aculeticarpa*, *Mimosa pudica*, *Nyctanthes arbor tristis*, *Prunus mahleb*, *Santalum album*, *Senna occidentalis*, *Styrax officinalis*, *Syzygium cumini*, *Zizyphus mauritiana*. Pollen slides of the plants collected were prepared by using Erdtman's acetolysis technique (1960).

Preparation of Pollen Slides by Acetolysis Technique (Erdtman, 1960)

For pollen slide preparation, polleniferous material / anthers of the flowering plants were picked with the help of a forceps into a test tube containing 70% alcohol. They were crushed with a glass rod and then filtered. The filtrate was centrifuged and to the

sediment 5ml. of Glacial acetic acid was added and centrifuged. The pollen sediment was processed by adding acetolysis mixture and mounting of the pollen grains was done in glycerine jelly. Three slides were prepared for each pollen type. Later the pollen slides were scanned under the microscope and morphological characters were studied according to the standard literature (Bhattacharya, *et al.*, (2015), Bhaskar, (1992), Erdtman, (1952). Punt, (2007), Nayar, (1990). Nair (1970). Pramanick, *et al.*, (2015). Perveen, & Qaiser, (2005). Panicker, & Sreedevi. (2004). Photomicrographs of the pollen types studied was taken by using a trinocular Olympus microscope attached with a digital camera.

Map I: showing Nagarkurnool district , Telangana State

Map II: Showing the Kollapur division of Nagarkurnool district, Telangana state, south India.

Results

The results of pollen morphological studies of fifteen flowering plants viz. *Alstonia scholaris*, *Cordia sebestena*, *Dichrostachis cinerea*, *Dodonea viscosa*, *Gyrocarpus americanus*, *Leucophyllum*

frutescens, *Mimosa aculeticarpa*, *Mimosa pudica*, *Nyctanthes arbor tristis*, *Prunus mahleb*, *Santalum album*, *Senna occidentalis*, *Styrax officinalis*, *Syzygium cumini*, *Zizyphus mauritiana* showed diversity in morphological

features. The pollen types varied in size, shape, apertural pattern and sporoderm ornamentation. Details regarding the phenology and the morphological characteristics of the pollen types are given below. Plate 1-4 shows the photomicrographs of the palynotaxa studied.

Pollen Morphological Characters and Phenology of Collected Plant Species:

1. *Senna occidentalis* (L.) Link.

English name: Coffee senna

Vernacular name: Kassinda

Flowering period: Throughout the year

Size, shape and symmetry - Pollen grains in monads, 46-48 amb triangular, 48 x 44 um, prolate spheroidal, isopolar, radially symmetrical.

Aperture- Tricolporate, colpi very narrowly elliptic, tips acute, ora-lalongate

Exine- 3um thick, tectate, surface ornamentation psilate.

2. *Cordia sebastena* L.

English name: Geiger tree

Vernacular name: Virigi

Flowering period: Throughout the year

Size, shape and symmetry - Pollen grains in monads, 41-45 um, amb spheroidal, 37 x 45um, oblate, isopolar, radially symmetrical

Aperture- Tricolporate, colpi is wide, tips acute, margins thick, ora circular

Exine- 2.5 um thick, pollen ornamentation reticulate, lumina polygonal

3. *Styrax officinalis* (L.)

English name: Styrax

Vernacular name: Storax or Snowbell

Flowering period: May-June

Size, shape and symmetry - Pollen grains monads, 40-45 um, amb rounded triangular, 30-32 x 40-45 um, oblate, isopolar, radially symmetrical

Aperture- Tricolporate, colpi wide, ora-lalongate

Exine- 2um thick, subtectate, surface ornamentation scabrate

4. *Leucophyllum frutescens* (Berland.) I.M. Johnst.

English name: Texas sage

Vernacular name: Purple sage

Flowering period: April-Aug

Size, shape and symmetry - Pollen grains-monads, 22 x 17 um, amb-25, rounded triangular, prolate, isopolar, radially symmetrical.

Aperture- Tricolporate, colpi long, elliptic, ora-circular, wide.

Exine- 1.5um, thick, subtectate, collumella distinct, surface ornamentation microreticulate

5. *Mimosa aculeaticarpa* Ortega

English name: Cat's Claws

Vernacular name: Attapatti

Flowering period: May-Aug, April-Sep

Size, shape and symmetry - Pollen grains in 8-celled polyads, individual grains 10-12 um in diameter

Aperture- Triporate, pores faint

Exine- 1.5 um thick, tectate, surface ornamentation psilate

6. *Mimosa pudica* L.

English name: Touch me not

Vernacular name: Attapatti

Flowering period: Throughout the year

Size, shape and symmetry - pollen grains in 8-12 um, tetrahedral, tetrads; spheroidal; radially symmetrical.

Aperture- Individual grains provided with 4-5 faint pores.

Exine- 1µm thick, tectate, surface ornamentation psilate.

7. *Alstonia scholaris* (L.) R. Br

English name: Devil's tree

Vernacular name: Edakulapala

Flowering period: Mar-July

Size, shape and symmetry - Pollen grains in monads, 13.5 , amb spheroidal, 21-22x 22-24 µm, oblate spheroidal, isopolar, radially symmetrical.

Aperture- Tricolporate, core margin thick, ora circular, thick, colpi fine.

Exine- 1.5 µm thick, sexine as thick as nexine, tectate, surface ornamentation psilate to granular

8. *Dodonaea viscosa* Jacq.

English name: Broadleaf hop bush

Vernacular name: Bandaru

Flowering period: April-Aug

Size, shape and symmetry - 29-33 μm , amb sub-triangular to rounded with slightly projecting obtuse angles, 28-32 x 26-29 μm , prolate spheroidal, radially symmetrical

Aperture- Tricolporate, colpi long and narrow almost reaching the pores, ora lalongate with nexinous thickenings.

Exine- 2 μm thick, subtectate, surface faintly microreticulate

9. *Gyrocarpus americanus* Jacq.

English name: Helicopter tree

Vernacular name: Poliki

Flowering name: Oct-Aprl

Size, shape and symmetry - Pollen grains in monads, 22 μm , amb spheroidal, 20 x 22 μm , sub-oblate isopolar, radially symmetrical.

Aperture- Tricolporate, colpi-fine, ora-incrassate.

Exine- 1-2 μm thick, tectate, surface ornamentation psilate

10. *Prunus mahaleb* L.

English name: Mahleb cherry

Vernacular name: Cherry tree

Flowering name: Dec-Mar

Size, shape and symmetry - Pollen grains in monads, 26-50 μm , amb triangular, 48-50x 28-32 μm , oblate, isopolar, radially symmetrical.

Aperture- Tricolporate, colpi wide, ora circular

Exine- 1 μm . thick, surface ornamentation perforate.

11. *Santalum album* L.

English name: Indian sandalwood

Vernacular name: Chandana

Flowering period: Dec-Aprl

Size, shape and symmetry - Pollen grain in monads, rounded triangular, 24-30 X 18-22 μm , sub prolate, isopolar radially symmetrical.

Aperture-Triporate, pore margins thick, incrassate, pore diameter 4-6 μm .

Exine- 1.5 μm thick, sub tectate, surface ornamentation psilate to granular.

12. *Dichrostachis cinerea* (Linn.) wt&Arn.

English name: Sicklebush

Vernacular name: Nalla veluturu chettu

Flowering period: Oct-Feb

Size, shape and symmetry - Pollen grain 28-30 μm , Amb triangular, isopolar, radially symmetrical.

Aperture-Triporate, pores with annulus

Exine- 2.5 μm thick, tectate, surface ornamentation verrucate.

13. *Nyctanthes arbor tristis* Linn.

English name: Night blooming jasmine

Vernacular name: Parijatha

Flowering peroid: Aug-Dec

Size, shape and symmetry - Polen grains in monads, 72-88 μm , Amb spheroidal, 65-86 x 60-74 μm , Sub-prolate, isopolar, radially symmetrical.

Aperture - Tricolpate, colpi linear, long tips acute, margins thick incrassate

Exine- 5-6 μm thick, subtectate, surface reticulate, piloid processes of two types (narrow & broad) lumina polygonal with free bacules, muri simplibaculate.

14. *Syzygium cumini* (Linn.) Skeels.

English name: Black plum

Vernacular name: Neredu

Flowering period: Mar-Aprl

Size, shape and symmetry - Pollen grains in monads, 16-18 μm , Amb triangular, occasionally quadrangular sides concave, 10 - 12 x 17-20 μm , oblate, isopolar, radially symmetrical

Aperture - Tricolporate, rarely tetracolporate, syncolpate, parasyncolpate ora-lalongate

Exine- 1.2 μm thick, tectate, surface psilate.

15. *Zizyphus mauritiana* Lam.

English name: Jujube

Vernacular name: Regu

Flowering period: July-Nov

Size, shape and symmetry - Pollen grains in monads, 18-22 μm , Amb triangular, sides 16-20 x 20-22 μm , sub-prolate, isopolar, radially symmetrical

Aperture-Tricolporate, colpi long, tips acute, or-lalongate

Exine-1.5 μm thick, tectate, surface psilate

<p><i>Alstonia scholaris</i></p>	<p><i>Alstonia scholaris</i></p>	<p><i>Alstonia scholaris</i></p>
<p><i>Cordia sebastena</i></p>	<p><i>Cordia sebastena</i></p>	<p><i>Cordia sebastena</i></p>
<p><i>Dichrostachis cinerea</i></p>	<p><i>Dichrostachis cinerea</i></p>	<p><i>Dichrostachis cinerea</i></p>
<p><i>Dodonia viscosa</i></p>	<p><i>Dodonia viscosa</i></p>	<p><i>Dodonia viscosa</i></p>

Plate 1: Photomicrographs of the pollen types studied (All figures x 1000 magnification)

<i>Gyrocarpus americanus</i>	<i>Gyrocarpus americanus</i>	<i>Gyrocarpus americanus</i>
<i>Leucophyllum frutescens</i>	<i>Leucophyllum frutescens</i>	<i>Leucophyllum frutescens</i>
<i>Mimosa aculeaticarpa</i>	<i>Mimosa aculeaticarpa</i>	<i>Mimosa aculeaticarpa</i>
<i>Mimosa pudica</i>	<i>Mimosa pudica</i>	<i>Mimosa pudica</i>

Plate: 2

<i>Nyctanthus orbor tristis</i>	<i>Nyctanthus orbor tristis</i>	<i>Nyctanthus orbor tristis</i>
<i>Prunus mahaleb</i>	<i>Prunus mahaleb</i>	<i>Prunus mahaleb</i>
<i>Santalum album</i>	<i>Santalum album</i>	<i>Santalum album</i>
<i>Senna occidentalis.</i>	<i>Senna occidentalis.</i>	<i>Senna occidentalis.</i>

Plate - 3

Plate: 4

Discussion

Pollen morphological studies of fifteen plant species of Kollapur revenue division of Nagarkurnool district of Telangana State was carried out during 2022-2023. These fifteen plant species were referable to thirteen families. All the species belongs to Dicotyledons. Pollen characters of the taxa studied showed diversity in their size, shape, apertural pattern and exine ornamentation. Pollen grains were mostly in monads but tetrads (*Mimosa pudica*) and octads (*Mimosa aculeaticarpa*) were also recorded. The shapes of all pollen grain varied from oblate, oblate-spheroidal, prolate, prolate-spheroidal to

spheroidal. Apertures were simple and composite types, colpate, porate and colporate aperture types were characterized in the pollen taxa. Out of 15 genera studied, tricolpate apertural pattern is dominant (67%) followed by triporate (27%) and tricolpate (6%) condition. The exine sculpturing patterns of the pollen taxa ranged from psilate, verrucate, microreticulate, reticulate, retipilate, striate-rugulate, and scabrate. **Psilate** exine ornamentation is exhibited by most of the genera(53.3%) studied viz., *Alstonia scholaris*, *Gyrocarpus americanus*, *Mimosa aculeaticarpa*, *Mimosa pudica*, *Senna occidentalis*, *Santalum album*, *Syzygium cumini*,

and *Zizyphus mauritiana* followed by **reticulate** (*Cordia sebastena* *Nyctanthes arbor tristis*) and **microreticulate** (*Dodonaea viscosa* *Leucophyllum frutescens*) (13.3% each), **scabrate** (*Styrax officinalis*), **perforate** (*Prunus mahaleb*), and **verrucate** (*Dichrostachis cineraria*) (6.6% each) types.

Conclusions

Pollen grains show diversity in their morphological characters often considered as fingerprints of nature and are used in the identification and in the delimitation of the taxa up to the species level. This study underscores the significant taxonomic value of detailed pollen morphological characterization of the flora of Kollapur revenue division of Nagarkurnool district of Telangana State.

Acknowledgements

Authors are thankful to the Principal, University college of science, Saifabad, Osmania University, Hyderabad for providing lab facilities.

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Source of support: Nil;

Conflict of interest: The authors declare no conflict of interests.

Cite this article as:

Pallati, C. and Kumar, M.J. "Pollen Characterization of Some Tropical Flora of Kollapur Revenue Division of Nagarkurnool District of Telangana State, South India." *Annals of Plant Sciences*.14.05 (2025): pp. 6832-6840.